

Real-time trajectory scaling algorithms for enhanced path following of robot manipulators

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Abstract—Trajectory scaling algorithms can improve the path-following performance of robot manipulators by modifying the trajectory online according to the actual state of the environment and other agents. This abstract discusses different methods recently proposed in the literature: it gives an overview of their capabilities and features and it compares the existing techniques both from a qualitative and experimental point of view.

I. INTRODUCTION

More and more often, robot manipulators have to work in unstructured environments or to cooperate with other agents (e.g., human operators). In the presence of dynamic obstacles and goals, motion planning needs to be performed according to the state of the environment at the current time instant. A common approach is to perform rough trajectory planning right before the robot movement. Then, the trajectory is modified online according to the environment state. This approach has two advantages: first, the initial planning phase can be faster, because only a rough, sub-optimal solution is required (the online algorithm will refine the solution at runtime); second, the online algorithm can quickly react to changes in the environment and to the behavior of other agents.

Online modification of the robot motion can be performed mainly in two different ways: by modifying the whole trajectory that the robot has to follow, or by modifying only the velocity profile, thus keeping the original path. The second option is often preferred because it only requires slowing down the execution of the trajectory along the same path. Therefore, it does not require devising a new collision-free path and it is way lighter from the computational point of view.

To this purpose, online trajectory scaling methods deform the original timing law to satisfy the robot constraints. The advantage is that the nominal motion can be devised without rigorously taking the robot limits into account, as the online algorithm will account for them at runtime. Online trajectory scaling is also useful in human-robot collaborative applications. For example, safe collaboration can be implemented by slowing down the robot speed according to safety constraints from the standard [1]. This has usually been implemented by means of danger zones where the robot speed is limited, but recent more advanced strategies modulate the speed dynamically. Trajectory scaling can be used to optimize the slowdown phase.

This abstract presents online trajectory scaling algorithms recently proposed in the literature and aims to give an overview

of the capabilities and the performance of such methods. To do so, we introduce the trajectory scaling problem (Section II) and we briefly expose the algorithms available in the literature (Section III). A qualitative evaluation based upon the different features of the algorithms is also provided to help the reader understand which method is more suitable according to the application requirements. An experimental comparison between the main classes of methods is also discussed (Section IV): a Universal Robots UR10 is tasked with a Cartesian path to be executed with different nominal times. The path-following error and the average execution time obtained with different scaling methods are compared.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider a path x_d in the operational space¹, parametrized with respect to the scalar variable γ such that:

$$x_d : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n, \gamma \mapsto x_d(\gamma). \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of degrees of freedom of the robot. The trend of γ with respect to time defines the timing law of the trajectory. Often, the timing law is given due to technological requirements (for example, constant-speed traits may be needed in the process), but it might be relaxed to ensure safety or to preserve the quality of the process.

Trajectory scaling algorithms allow the relaxation of the timing law by using $\dot{\gamma}$ as a control variable. In particular, given a velocity profile $\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ref}}$ and denoting with q the robot joint configuration, the timing law can be chosen online by solving the following control problem at each time instant t_0 :

$$\underset{q,v}{\text{minimize}} \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \left\| x_d(\gamma(t)) - f(q) \right\|_Q^2 + \left\| u(t) - v \right\|_R^2 dt \quad (2)$$

subject to $\dot{\gamma} = v$ and the robot limitations (e.g., joint range, velocity, acceleration, and torque limits), where $u = \dot{\gamma}_{\text{ref}}$, f is the forward kinematic function of the robot, Q and R are weighting matrices, $\|x\|_Q^2 = x^T Q x$. Additional constraints can be added to account, for example, for safety limits in human-robot collaboration.

III. PROPOSED APPROACHES

Several approaches have been recently proposed in the literature. They can be classified into two main categories, that is, *look ahead* and *non-look ahead* methods:

- Non-look ahead methods (also referred to as *local*), such as [2], [3], [4], [5], which only concern the trajectory and the robot state at time t_0 . In other words, (2) is approximated by considering the control error and the control effort

¹The joint-space case can be seen as a subcase of the operational space.

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TABLE I: Comparison between the proposed TAMP approach and other works in the literature.

	speed limits	accel. limits	torque limits	higher order constr.	look-ahead	optimization free	computational time	Cartesian traject.	Redundancy
[2], [3]	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	$\sim \mu\text{s}$		
[4]	✓	✓				✓	$\sim \mu\text{s}$	✓	
[5]	✓					✓	$\sim \mu\text{s}$	✓	✓
[6]	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	$\sim \mu\text{s}$	✓	
[7], [8]	✓	✓	✓		✓		$\sim \text{ms}$		
[9]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	$\sim \text{ms}$		
[10]	✓	✓			✓		$\sim \text{ms}$	✓	✓

only at the current time instant t_0 . These methods are characterized by low computational burdens, but they do not take into account future information about the tasks or the robot constraints. This results in sub-optimal solutions in terms of process throughput and quality (*i.e.*, the scaling is not able to avoid path deformation).

- Look-ahead techniques (also referred to as *predictive*), such as [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], which consider the optimization of the path following along a future time horizon. As a consequence, they give much better solutions but have higher computational burdens.

Table I compares some of the methods presented in the literature based on some features that may characterize their choice in real-world applications, that is:

- the **constraints** the method can include (*e.g.*, some methods can only manage joint speed limits, while others can include limits on jerk or the derivative of the torque).
- whether the method is local or **look-ahead**.
- the **computational time** for a standard robot manipulator (*e.g.*, six degrees of freedom).
- whether the method can be implemented **without** using **mathematical programming** (as the need for optimization tools may be a limit to the implementation in commercial hardware such as industrial controllers).
- whether the method is suitable also for **Cartesian trajectories**.
- whether the method can exploit the **kinematic redundancy** of the manipulator (*e.g.*, to optimize a secondary objective).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON

This section provides an experimental comparison of different methods to give an idea of the performance achievable with different techniques. We consider a 6-degree-of-freedom robot, UR10, which is required to follow a Cartesian path that consists in the stylized profile of the word *CNR* in the yz -plane. The task is an example of a manufacturing task, such as gluing or laser cutting, along complex shapes. During the task, the end-effector orientation should be orthogonal to the yz -plane. The nominal timing law γ^0 is a seven-trait-acceleration function. Except for the initial and final part of the trajectory, the longitudinal velocity of the timing law is constant, as typical of gluing and cutting. Details on the experiments are given in [6].

TABLE II: Translation error and execution time for different nominal trajectory times t_f .

t_f [s]	e_{\max} [m]		t_{real}/t_f	
	local	look-ahead	local	look-ahead
5.0	$5.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.08	1.05
4.0	$1.78 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.98 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.20	1.14
3.0	$4.65 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.45	1.31
2.0	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.99 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.58	1.93

We run tests with different values of the desired execution time t_f : smaller values of t_f correspond to more demanding trajectories, as the same path should be covered in a smaller time. This requires a heavier scaling for the robot to follow the path accurately.

We compare a **local** (*i.e.*, non-look ahead) [5] and a **look-ahead** method [6]. The maximum and path-following errors, e_{\max} , are shown in Table II. In all cases, the look-ahead method significantly outperforms the local one. In the least demanding task ($t_f = 5$ s), its error is around ten times smaller than the one of the local method; in the most demanding case ($t_f = 2$ s), this difference grows up to three orders of magnitude. Regarding the execution time, Table II also shows the ratio between the actual time taken by the robot to perform the task, t_{real} and the nominal time, t_f . As expected, the look-ahead method is able to reduce the velocity scaling and performs the trajectories in a shorter time compared to the local method.

Videos of this and other similar experiments can be found at the following links^{2,3,4}

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²<https://youtu.be/tm5phfM6FNw>

³<https://youtu.be/ks5uYQF6kyA>

⁴https://youtu.be/tZYk_CK6kjI